

3 **A farewell to glaciers: Ecosystem services loss in the Spanish Pyrenees**

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11 **ABSTRACT**

12 Glaciers are long-term freshwater reservoirs that contribute to the regulation
13 of water availability throughout the year. In the Pyrenees mountain range,
14 glaciers are predicted to disappear by the mid 21st century if current melting
15 trends continue. The areas downstream from these glaciers have seen a
16 gradual increase in water consumption since the 1980s, mainly due to the
17 conversion of traditional crops to more water-demanding products,
18 expansion of the irrigated agricultural area, and modernization of agricultural
19 techniques that create incentives to spread water use. The steady increase of
20 water consumption is not compatible with the predicted future scenario,
21 where a reduced provision of water as an essential ecosystem service is
22 expected, in particular during the dry summers. In this study, we present an
23 up-to-date outlook on the evolution of the glaciers on the Spanish side of the
24 Pyrenees. We then calculate the melting rate (in volume) of these glaciers in
25 order to estimate their water contributions to their respective watersheds.
26 These results are combined with existing data on water consumption for each
27 watershed, and aiming to offer a more sustainable future for the local
28 population, we propose a set of adaptive measures that have been
29 implemented in other regions where water availability has gradually become
30 an issue. These measures are focused on diversifying the most water-
31 consuming activity in the region (agriculture) to enable a future compatible
32 with the ecosystem services the region is able to provide.

33

34 **1. Introduction**

35 Beyond being the basic substance for the functioning of most eco- systems,
36 the availability and reliable supply of water is an increasingly important issue
37 faced by societies all over the world. As a critical component of agricultural
38 and industrial production, energy (hydro- power), recreation, and household
39 consumption, water is fundamental for both the economy and human
40 livelihoods (Bolch, 2017). Shortages on water availability can be also the
41 source of social and political ten- sions that may develop into instability or
42 even grave conflicts (e.g. Lonergan, 2018). Challenges related to the
43 provision of water are expected to increase in the face of future climate
44 change scenarios (e.g. Hijioka et al., 2014).

45 Glaciers are long-term freshwater reservoirs that accumulate water during
46 snowfall and release it only when temperatures increase (Bolch, 2017). This
47 time frame differential, typically in a seasonal cycle (e.g. accumulation
48 through autumn and winter, and release during spring and summer), allows
49 for glaciers to reliably provide water when is more needed, which can be
50 considered a crucial ecosystem service (Rumbaer et al., 2015). This is an
51 important feature particularly in regions with long and dry summers, such as
52 the Mediterranean Basin. Under these conditions, glaciers play a crucial role
53 in mitigating the effects of droughts within their watersheds when other
54 water sources decline (Van Tiel et al., 2018).

55 Within the Mediterranean Basin, the Pyrenees mountain range lies across the
56 isthmus that separates Spain and France, forming the physical and political
57 border between these two countries. It extends for almost 500 km,
58 connecting the Atlantic Ocean to the Mediterranean Sea. Presently, 19
59 glaciers are found in the Pyrenees, covering an area of 2.42 km². Eight of
60 these glaciers are located on the Spanish side of the Pyrenees while the other
61 eight are located on the French side (Fig. 1). Nevertheless, all of them are
62 found along an approximately 100 km long line in the central part of the
63 mountains, where the peaks are higher than 3000 m (Serrat and Ventura,
64 2005). The 2 largest of these glaciers is the Aneto Glacier, extending over
65 0.561 km (Rico et al., 2017). Since the northern slopes of the Pyrenees
66 receive considerable precipitation (approximately between 700 and 1100
67 mm annually according to climate-data.org), in this study we focus on the
68 consequences of glacier disappearance on the southern slopes, which are
69 characterized by a dry Mediterranean climate (precipitations of

70 approximately between 350 and 700 mm annually according to climate-
71 data.org).

72 Due to the dry summer period, communities living in the Mediterranean area
73 are especially vulnerable to water shortages. Particularly in the watersheds
74 draining from the Southern slopes of the Pyrenees, water is a scarce resource
75 used mainly in household consumption, agriculture, livestock husbandry
76 (including aquaculture), industry, hydropower, and recreation (CHE, 2016).
77 Following national legislation (Decreto 638/2016, de 9 de diciembre), the
78 entities in charge of water management in the different river basins of Spain
79 specify, for each river (and within rivers, for each section of the river), a
80 minimum volume necessary for the river ecosystems to survive called
81 environmental flow, and only the water that exceeds that volume may be
82 used. The eight glaciers in this study drain into the rivers Gallego, Cinca,
83 Esera (a tributary of the Cinca River), Garonne (in France, via complex
84 karstic conduction), and Noguera-Ribagorzana, with environmental flows
85 stipulated at the end of each river ranging from 2.00 to 4.61 m³ s⁻¹. The
86 remaining useable water to cover the demand created from household
87 consumption, industry, and agriculture and livestock husbandry on the
88 watersheds of the four Spanish rivers is remarkably limited, and in years of
89 extreme drought, the smaller communities in this region undergo water
90 restrictions for household consumption. Moreover, due to climate change, it
91 is estimated that in the next 30 years, there will be a reduction of between
92 4% and 21% of water flowing through these watersheds (Frederick, 1997).

93 In the face of the predicted disappearance of the glaciers in the Pyrenees
94 (Gonzalez Trueba et al., 2008) within the next 30 years, and seeing the
95 present limitations of the region to guarantee a sufficient provision of water,
96 in this study, we analyze the regional context aiming to find
97 recommendations that can support the decision-makers improving the
98 ecosystem service provision (focused on the provision of water) as well as
99 efficiency in water use. Although the disappearance of the Pyrenean glaciers
100 will have negative effects on cultural ecosystem services such as landscape
101 aesthetics or historical value, given the importance of water in the dry
102 Mediterranean climate of the region of study, in this work we focus on the
103 provision of water as the main ecosystem service that will be lost. Section 2
104 describes the methods followed and the sources of data used in this study.
105 Section 3 provides an overview of the existing literature related to the

106 Pyrenean glaciers and the estimates of water contribution of each glacier to
107 its corresponding watershed. Section 4 describes the water availability and
108 how water is used in the study area. In section 5 we propose and discuss a
109 set of alternatives, and section 6 brings forward our conclusion.

110

111 2. Methods and sources of data

112 This study followed a three steps process. In the first step, we conducted a
113 thorough literature review to assess the evolution and present status of the
114 Pyrenean glaciers. To that end, we conducted a computerized search (using
115 Google Scholar and ScienceDirect search engines) applying the terms
116 “southern Pyrenees”, “Spanish Pyrenees”, “glacier evolution”, “glacier
117 melt”, “glaciers”. To select the relevant works, we focused on studies
118 published within the last 30 years, and we selected the studies that provided
119 data for all Pyrenean glaciers (or at least for all glaciers in the Spanish side
120 of the Pyrenees) rather than those studies that provided data on only some of
121 those glaciers.

122 During the previous step, we could confirm that there is a lack of accurate
123 and up-to-date data on glacier volume loss, and thus, water contribution of
124 these glaciers to their respective watersheds. Therefore, our second step
125 consisted on estimating this information from data collected from different
126 sources (e.g. extrapolation of volume loss from nearby glaciers, estimation
127 of volume loss from published areas and thickness loss). Each one of those
128 sources has its own limitations, and thus, our final estimation of glacier
129 volume loss is bound to a number of uncertainties. For example, the
130 estimation of volume of ice lost using field measurements does not always
131 yield accurate data, because an ice density needs to be assumed in order to
132 convert volume change to mass change (Huss, 2013). When using aerial
133 images to estimate volume loss, low quality image datasets should be
134 considered with caution given the high uncertainties in the altimetry
135 restitution process, and the uncertainties derived from the image resolution,
136 which affects the image georeferencing process (e.g. Marti et al., 2015).
137 Moreover, the accuracy in the location of the control points (normally easily
138 identifiable from rocks and cliffs around glaciers) is key to obtain an
139 acceptable horizontal root-mean-square error (RMSE). Since there is no
140 information on how each dataset dealt with these uncertainties, our

141 estimations based on the combination of information from different datasets
142 is not expected to provide accurate results. Nevertheless, the results provided
143 are in line with observations, and are the only available values to date.

144 After estimating the volumes of ice lost, we merged these contributions with
145 data collected from individual reports published by the Ebro Hydrographical
146 Confederation (CHE for its acronym in Spanish), the entity in charge of
147 water management in the larger river basin in which the four river watersheds
148 understudy (Gallego, Cinca, Esera, and Noguera-Ribagorzana) are
149 integrated. The data collected from CHE refers to mean river flows,
150 environmental flows, the volume of water necessary to satisfy household
151 demand in each river watershed, the volume of water used for agriculture,
152 the volume of water used for industry, river watershed areas, and population
153 served with water from each watershed. From these merged data we derived
154 for each river the flow without glacier contributions, estimated flow
155 reduction due to climate change based on a conservative value (12.5%) taken
156 from the range of 4–21% indicated by (Frederick, 1997), and from those
157 values, we also estimated the remaining water flow that could be used for
158 household consumption.

159 The third, and last step, consisted of conducting a new literature review to
160 determine, on the one hand, the pros and cons of the irrigation techniques
161 and the types of crops used in the area of study, and on the other hand, to
162 learn from previous experiences from other regions of the world that undergo
163 water-related issues. For the first objective (water techniques and types of
164 crops used) we reviewed the available govern- mental reports from the
165 watersheds within the area of study, and con- ducted a computerized search
166 applying the terms “southern Pyrenees”, “Spanish Pyrenees”, “Huesca”,
167 “Aragon”, “water” “irrigation” “agriculture”. We then selected the
168 publications that provided information related to our study. For the second
169 objective (learning from previous experiences in other regions), we
170 conducted a new computerized search applying the terms “drought”, “water
171 issues”, “alternative uses to agriculture”, “water management”. We then
172 again selected the relevant publications that provided information that could
173 help us bring forward a set of recommendations (Fig. 2).

174

175 3. Evolution of the pyrenean glaciers

176 Due to their relatively small size, the Pyrenean glaciers have not been as
177 widely studied as other glaciers in more prominent mountain ranges.
178 Nevertheless, these glaciers play a role in the hydrology dynamics of the
179 region, and a few authors have addressed the challenge of measuring the ice
180 cover at different times in the past decades. As such, while most publications
181 assess the changes experienced by the glaciers through time (Chueca et al.,
182 2008, 2007; 2005; Dessens and Bücher, 1995; Feuillet and Mercier, 2012;
183 García-Ruiz et al., 2014; Gonzalez Trueba et al., 2008; Grove and Gellatly,
184 1995; Lopez-Moreno, 2005; Lopez-Moreno et al., 2016; Marti et al., 2015),
185 several others provide information on particular glaciers' morphology or ice
186 volume in a specific point in time (Arenillas et al., 1991; Chueca and Julian,
187 2010; Martinez, 1989; Pastor, 2013; Rico et al., 2017; Serrano and Martín-
188 Moreno, 2018). Moreover, other publications deal with the methods,
189 techniques or data necessary to provide adequate measurements of the
190 glaciers (Chueca and Julian, 2004; Deaux et al., 2014; del Río et al., 2014;
191 Lopez-Moreno et al., 2019; Sanjose et al., 2014).

192 A study referring to the presence and extension of the Pyrenean glaciers as
193 of 1984 (Serrat and Ventura, 2005) showed that in that year, there were 411
194 glaciers in the Pyrenees (27 on the French side, and 14 on the Spanish side),
195 and the total area occupied by those glaciers was 8.10 km². A more recent
196 publication (Rico et al., 2017) offered an update of the 1984 data, providing
197 insights on the alarming melting rate of the glaciers in the Pyrenees mountain
198 range. This publication showed that as of 2016, only 19 glaciers remained in
199 the Pyrenees (11 on the French side, and 8 on the Spanish side), covering a
200 total area of 2.42 km². Focusing on the Spanish side of the mountains, in
201 1984, the existing glaciers covered an area of 3.96 km². By 2016, 6 of the
202 glaciers had disappeared completely and the remaining area covered by ice
203 was just 1.54 km² (Table 1). Following the melting trends, the last glacier in
204 the Pyrenees is predicted to disappear around the year 2050 (Gonzalez
205 Trueba et al., 2008).

206 From a volumetric point of view, the data gathered show that the Aneto
207 Glacier has the highest melting rate (more than double the melting rate of the
208 closest rate), providing a considerably higher water contribution to its
209 watershed than any of the other glaciers. Due to a lack of available data, the
210 annual volume of ice lost by the Infierno Glacier was calculated using data
211 of ice wastage (annual loss in meters of water equivalent) from the Ossue

212 Glacier (France), an extensively monitored glacier located 9 km away, and
213 with a similar altitude and slope orientation. We followed the same process
214 for the Llardana and la Paul Glaciers, assimilating their volume loss rate to
215 that of the Maladeta Glacier, which stands at a distance of 16 km, and has a
216 similar altitude and slope orientation (Table 2).

217 Although all the above-mentioned publications address the measuring of the
218 ice cover in one way or another, none of them go beyond the measuring in
219 order to analyze the consequences that the loss of ice mass has (and will
220 have) over the socio-ecological systems of the area of influence.
221 Nevertheless, Lopez-Moreno et al. (2008) offered an overview of the
222 changes in patterns of water management practices in the same area of study.
223 The study highlights the inadequacy of past water management measures to
224 confront the future water limitations anticipated by the projections based on
225 predicted climate change scenarios. The main inadequate measures pointed
226 out in that study were the enlargement of irrigation areas, the promotion of
227 crops with high water requirements aimed to combat saline soils, and the
228 management of dams focused on satisfying agricultural demands without
229 regard for annual water availability or river flows. However, the study does
230 not offer alternatives to the present inadequate water management. Aiming
231 to cover this gap of knowledge, in our work we built on the results obtained
232 by the publications mentioned, we focused on suggesting measures to
233 counteract the negative effects on the provision of ecosystem services that
234 the loss of the Pyrenean glaciers will have in the next 30 years over the area
235 of influence.

236

237 4. Water availability and use on the southern slopes of the Spanish Pyrenees

238 The glaciers on the Spanish Pyrenees discharge into the Gallego, Cinca,
239 Esera (a tributary of the Cinca River), Garonne (in France, by karstic
240 conduction), and Noguera-Ribagorzana. Focusing on the rivers that flow
241 over the southern slopes of the Pyrenees, our study includes the Gallego,
242 Cinca (including Esera), and Noguera-Ribagorzana Watersheds, the three of
243 them tributary of the Ebro River Basin. The Spanish Ministry for Ecological
244 Transition (Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica), through its organization
245 CHE, manages all issues related to hydraulics and hydrology within the Ebro
246 River Basin, which discharges into the Mediterranean Sea. From reports

247 published by CHE regarding the river watersheds under study, we collected
248 data related to mean and environmental flow volumes, and volumes of water
249 used for household consumption, agriculture, and industry. The data shows
250 that presently, the supply of water is just enough to cover the demand, with
251 a little additional volume to spare. Extracting from the present volumes the
252 contributions from the glaciers (predicted to disappear in the next years) and
253 the reductions of volume due to predicted influence of climate change, the
254 results show that in the near future (within the next 30 years), all three
255 watersheds will undergo water shortages (Table 3). These values take into
256 account present volumes of water used. Since these volumes have been
257 steadily increasing in the past (CHE, 2020), the values here presented are an
258 underestimation of the volumes of water that will be demanded in within the
259 next decades.

260

261 5. Discussion and proposal of alternatives

262 In view of the climate trends that predict higher mean annual temperatures
263 and reduced annual precipitation in the region of study (e. g. Buendia et al.,
264 2016; Lorenzo-Lacruz et al., 2012), it is difficult to compile a future scenario
265 where the Pyrenean glaciers will not disappear within the next few decades.
266 Losing these natural water reservoirs will add further constraints on water
267 availability in a region already affected by a significant reduction in the
268 trends of snow accumulation (Lopez-Moreno et al., 2008). In this study, we
269 raise awareness of some of the effects that glacier disappearance will have
270 downstream, and we provide recommendations addressed to improve water
271 use. The aim of these recommendations is to help mitigate the negative
272 effects of losing such important ecosystem service providers, the glaciers.

273 The risks posed by the continuous reduction of water availability while water
274 demand increases, extend not only over the local and regional ecosystems,
275 but also over the livelihoods of the communities living in the area. These
276 risks include, but are not limited to, ecosystem degradation, economic losses,
277 social unrest, disproportionate emigration, conflicts, etc. The
278 recommendations we propose, aim to provide a basis to minimize those risks,
279 and to establish a series of resilience mechanisms in the region that will help
280 to respond to the perturbations brought as a consequence of the dramatic
281 reduction of water availability. By promoting ecosystem improvement and a

282 wider distribution of economic gains, these recommendations should help
283 local communities not only to resist damage, but also to quickly recover
284 when disturbances occur.

285 A literature review offered insights on how water-related issues have been
286 addressed in other regions of the world, especially in countries where water
287 scarcity is a growing concern. Moreover, a review of literature in alternative
288 uses of ecosystem services served us to provide a set of measures that can be
289 used to directly or indirectly reduce the consumption of water in the region,
290 while providing a more sustainable future for the local inhabitants, in
291 particular in the rural areas characterized by limited opportunities.

292 We focused on the agricultural sector, the major water user in the study
293 region (97.0% of the total water extracted). Although water is also used for
294 recreation and hydropower in the study region, the water for these uses is not
295 extracted from the river, and therefore, we did not consider these uses.
296 According to the individual reports elaborated by CHE for each river
297 watershed (CHE, 2008, 2007a; 2007b, 2007c), in total, the four river
298 watersheds included in this study (Gallego, Cinca, Esera, and Noguera-
299 Ribagorzana) have 327,795 ha of agriculture under irrigation. The main
300 crops produced are pastures and herbaceous mainly used as livestock feed
301 (e.g. alfalfa), cereals (e.g. maize, wheat, barley), fruits (e.g. peach, apple),
302 grapes, and other vegetables (mainly at household scale for self-
303 consumption). The three main irrigation techniques used are flood, spray,
304 and drip. Flood irrigation has a water use efficiency of 60% (for every 1000
305 l of water used, 400 l are lost through evapotranspiration and other losses),
306 while spray irrigation in Mediterranean conditions has an efficiency of
307 70%, and drip irrigation has an efficiency of 90%, considering that the
308 irrigation system is properly designed and built (Moya Talens, 2009). Lecina
309 et al. (2010) explain that with the progressive adoption of modern irrigation
310 techniques, pastures and herbaceous crops have been gradually taking over
311 the production of winter cereals, the traditional crops of the region. Pastures
312 and herbaceous have higher water requirements than cereals, which together
313 with the gradual expansion of irrigated lands, have significantly increased
314 water consumption in the region since the 1980s (Lecina et al., 2010).

315 Since 2002, the national and regional governments of Spain have made
316 significant investments to modernize the irrigation sector, including
317 improvements on the infrastructure used for water distribution, and the

318 promotion of water-efficient technologies, mainly drip and spray(Gonzalez-
319 Cebollada,2015;KoechandLangat,2018).These technologies use less water
320 per surface unit and have other benefits such as optimization of
321 agrochemicals distribution and reduction of fertilizer use (Lopez-Gunn et al.,
322 2012). However, water-efficient technologies also have drawbacks that
323 should be considered. These technologies are expensive to install and
324 maintain, and their functioning requires energy inputs (i.e. electricity) that
325 increase greenhouse gas emissions (Ahmad and Khan, 2017). Moreover,
326 switching to these technologies changes agricultural patterns and practices,
327 including the use of more water-demanding crops and the expansion of the
328 agricultural frontier. As a consequence, in general, the adoption of water-
329 efficient technologies results in higher water consumption at a regional level
330 (Gonzalez-Cebollada, 2015).

331 A steady increase in water consumption in the region is not compatible with
332 the gradual decrease of water availability we presented in this study. Aiming
333 to balance natural resources consumption with the predicted reduction in
334 water availability in the area of study in the near future (within the next 30
335 years), in the following paragraphs we propose a set of measures based on
336 previous experiences from other locations. The set of measures proposed is
337 not a comprehensive list, but it might serve as a source of ideas to take new
338 directions. These measures are a diversification of the present agricultural
339 practices, to which it should be added the promotion of good practices at
340 household and industry level and the prevention of further environmental
341 pollution.

342 The first measure we propose consists of switching to less water- demanding
343 crops. The main reason in the region for the increase of water consumption
344 related to agriculture is the enlargement of irrigation areas along with the
345 introduction and use of crops with high water requirements (Causape et al.,
346 2004). Keeping in mind the different characteristics within the region (e.g.
347 soil type, microclimate), and based on the experiences published by the
348 Government of Aragon (Gobierno de Aragon, 2007), some of the low water
349 requirements crops proposed are oilseed rape (*Brassica napus*), chickpea
350 (*Cicer arietinum*), lentil (*Lens culinaris*), pea (*Pisum sativum*), ervil (*Vicia*
351 *ervilia*), triticale (*Triticum aestivum*) rye (*Secale cereale*) vetch (*Vicia*
352 *sativa*), barley (*Hor- deum vulgare*), wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), oat (*Avena*
353 *sativa*), linseed (*Linum usitatissimum*), safflower (*Carthamus tinctorius*),

354 and sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*). However, this is not a comprehensive
355 list; it merely aims to provide examples of crop species that could substitute
356 some of the presently used crops with high water requirements, such as
357 alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*) or maize (*Zea mais*). Switching to less water-
358 demanding crops is a measure considered a sustainable agricultural and land
359 management practice by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the
360 United Nations (FAO, 2015), and it has been proposed in other regions as an
361 agricultural adaptation to challenges in water availability (e.g. Feola et al.,
362 2017; Mvena, 2016). Although this measure would likely yield a lower
363 economic output per surface unit, a more specific analysis of costs and
364 benefits including the rising costs of water and irrigation systems would
365 provide specific figures for each particular case. Moreover, below we
366 provide additional measures that applied in combination could help balance
367 the possible initial economic losses of switching to less water-demanding
368 crops.

369 Another measure we propose related to the agricultural sector is shifting
370 from the dominating intensive livestock production system to a more
371 traditional extensive livestock production system. Taking pig production as
372 an example, between 2015 and 2017 intensive pig farms in Aragon increased
373 by 1000 pigs per day, reaching approximately 7.3 million pigs in 2017, and
374 Catalonia had approximately 0.5 million pigs more in the same year (FCO,
375 2017). This situation has created environmental challenges, some of them
376 directly related to water. For example, besides the increase in water
377 consumption, the CHE calculates that 64% of the farms within its
378 management area (most of them in Aragon and Catalonia) pollute the
379 superficial and underground waters with 129 tonnes of nitrogen per year
380 (CHE, 2018). This situation has contributed to the triggering of social unrest
381 and conflicts between local populations, intensive farm owners, and the
382 government (Barluenga, 2019). Alternatively, livestock production based on
383 extensive systems is generally considered an environmentally sustainable
384 practice with positive socio-cultural outcomes (e.g. Broom, 2017; Horrillo et
385 al., 2016). Moreover, in the Spanish Pyrenees, it was found that under
386 grazing as a consequence of the disappearance of extensive livestock
387 production has led some areas to become ‘green deserts’ with degraded
388 pastoral resources, reduced landscape diversity, and greater risk of wildfire
389 (Nadal-Romero et al., 2018).

390 The next measure we propose is the promotion of Non-Wood Forest Products
391 (NWFP). According to the annual forestry statistics report of the Spanish
392 Government (MAPA, 2017), 55% of Aragon and 63% of Catalonia are forest
393 lands. As NWFP, Aragon produces mainly mushrooms, truffles, and resin,
394 while Catalonia produces mainly cork, pine nuts, mushrooms, and truffles.
395 However, given the extension of forest lands in both regions, there is room
396 for expansion, innovation, and improvements in the sector. Following the
397 findings described in Ludvig et al. (2016), the typical enterprises emerging
398 in the NWFP sector are small-scale and family-owned that support rural
399 development increasing landowners income. These characteristics could
400 potentially balance the negative effects of reducing the amount of water
401 demanding crops, or of decreasing the numbers of intensive livestock
402 production farms in the rural areas of Aragon and Catalonia. NWFP is
403 currently being promoted in Europe (e.g. Huber et al., 2019; Wiersum et al.,
404 2018; Zivojinovic et al., 2017) and in other regions of the world (e.g.
405 Carpena et al., 2016; Pandey et al., 2016; Rawat et al., 2016) as an alternative
406 source of income and resources for rural communities.

407 We also propose promoting ecotourism and rural tourism practices to
408 diversify the present regional economy based on agricultural production.
409 Tourism in rural areas, and in particular in remote areas with a short range of
410 development options, is often regarded as a solution to boost local economies
411 (Huang et al., 2016). Areas without particularly beautiful landscapes can
412 develop other focus of interest such as gastronomy or wine tasting, learning
413 of traditional practices, outdoor sports, general rural quietness, heritage, and
414 many others. Although rural tourism and ecotourism are not new options in
415 the region of study (the Rural Tourism Federation of Aragon was founded in
416 1996), the statistics show that the demand for these services is steadily
417 increasing (Generalitat de Catalunya, 2019a; IAEST, 2019). Studies in other
418 European settings have shown that the promotion of rural tourism helped
419 local communities to cope with economic challenges while improving
420 demographic, cultural, and sustainability issues at the same time (Ambrus et
421 al., 2018; Petrovic et al., 2018).

422 An additional measure we propose is the promotion of Designation of Origin
423 (D.O.) labelled products. Such products are normally agricultural products
424 and their derivatives (e.g. wine, cheese, honey, meat) that have been
425 produced under strict controls of quality and provenance to guarantee the

426 highest quality. These controls are regulated at European level by the
427 Regulation (EU) 1151/2012 and the Regulation (EU) 1308/ 2013 of the
428 European Parliament and the Council. According to the Government of
429 Aragon (Gobierno de Aragon, 2019), the region presently counts with D.O.
430 labelling for wine (Calatayud, Campo de Borja, Cariñena, Somontano, Ayles,
431 and Cava), olive oil (Aceite del Bajo Aragon, and Aceite Sierra del
432 Moncayo), onions (Cebolla Fuentes de Ebro), ham (Jamon de Teruel), and
433 peach (Melocoton de Calanda). The Government of Catalonia (Generalitat
434 de Catalunya, 2019b) lists the regional D.O. products as wine (Penedes, Terra
435 Alta, Tarragona, Conca de Barbera, Costers del Segre, Emporda, Montsant,
436 Priorat, Alella, and Pla de Bages), rice (Arros del Delta de l'Ebre), hazelnut
437 (Avellana de Reus), beans (Fesols de Santa Pau and Mongeta del Ganxet),
438 cheese (Formatge de l'Alt Urgell i la Cerdanya), olive oil (Les Garrigues,
439 Oli de l'Emporda, Oli del Baix Ebre-- Montsia, Oli de Terra Alta, and
440 Siurana), butter (Mantega de l'Alt Urgell i la Cerdanya), and pear (Pera de
441 Lleida). Results of different studies show that products with D.O. labelling
442 are more valued by consumers (Marcoz et al., 2016), which helps to improve
443 the position of small-scale producers (Chamorro et al., 2015; Tregear et al.,
444 2016). Thus, the promotion of these products could potentially enhance the
445 regional rural economies of the study area.

446 The measures we propose above (switching to less water-demanding crops,
447 shifting from intensive to extensive livestock production, pro- motion of
448 Non-Wood Forest Products, promoting ecotourism and rural tourism, and
449 promotion of D.O. labelled products) require agreements and a common
450 understanding of the issues at hand from the public (e.g. regional and local
451 governments) and private sectors (e.g. large and small scale farmers, food
452 distributors, tourism entrepreneurs). Agreements and efforts in this direction
453 could encompass meetings and workshops between government officials and
454 stakeholders, aiming to clarify the issues and needs perceived by the latter
455 group; or elaboration and implementation of policies designed to address
456 such issues and needs (e. g. tax reduction for certain practices or products,
457 stronger representation of stakeholder groups in decision-making, flexibility
458 to adapt certain activities to different times of the year according to each
459 year's climate or other characteristics). Although some of the combined
460 efforts will be economic in nature (and therefore, predictably harder to
461 discuss), other efforts might be easier to arrange provided there is in place a
462 structure for effective communication between the public and private sectors.

463

464 6. Conclusion

465 The data presented shows that, in the near future (within the next 30 years),
466 there will be a water deficit in the area of study. Thus, we propose a set of
467 measures to palliate the negative consequences that the reduction on the
468 availability of this ecosystem service will have over the local population. The
469 measures proposed here require synergies and combined efforts from both
470 the private and the public sector. The adoption of different agricultural
471 techniques, the maintenance of traditional practices, and the promotion of
472 alternative activities and products need the support of adequate regulations
473 and public policies if the private land managers are to apply them. This
474 combination of efforts from the public and private sector is a challenging but
475 necessary task.

476

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484 CRediT authorship contribution statement

485 Nelson Grima: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis,
486 Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Supervision, Vali-
487 dation, Visualization, Writing - original draft. Nestor Campos: Data
488 curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation,
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494 Appendix A. Supplementary data

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497

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771
772 Fig. 1. Location of the existing glaciers on the Spanish side of the Pyrenees

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774
775 Fig. 2. Flow chart of the methods implemented during this study.

776

777 Table 1. Comparison of the presence and extension of the glaciers in the
778 Spanish Pyrenees in 1984 and in 2016. The abbreviation “G.” indicates
779 “Glaciar”, the Spanish word for “Glacier” (data sources: Serrat and
780 Ventura, 2005; and Rico et al., 2017).

Name	Watershed	Area 1984 [km ²]	Area 1994 [km ²]*	Area 2004 [km ²]*	Area 2016 [km ²]	Loss [km ²]	Loss [%]
G. del Infierno	Gállego	0.150	0.119	0.088	0.057	0.093	62.0
G. de Monte Perdido	Cinca	0.480	0.446	0.412	0.378	0.102	21.3
G. del Cilindro	Cinca	0.050	0.033	0.017	0.000	Vanished	100.0
G. de Marboré	Cinca	0.070	0.047	0.023	0.000	Vanished	100.0
G. de Robiñera	Cinca	0.050	0.033	0.017	0.000	Vanished	100.0
G. de Llardana	Cinca	0.230	0.179	0.127	0.076	0.154	67.0
G. de La Paul	Ésera	0.113	0.093	0.072	0.052	0.061	54.0
G. de Posets	Ésera	0.130	0.087	0.043	0.000	Vanished	100.0
G. de la Maladeta	Ésera	0.600	0.498	0.396	0.294	0.306	51.0
G. de Aneto	Ésera	1.320	0.987	0.774	0.561	0.759	57.5
G. de Coronas	Ésera	0.130	0.087	0.043	0.000	Vanished	100.0
G. de Barrancs	Garonne (karstic conduction)	0.280	0.202	0.123	0.045	0.235	83.9
G. de Tempestades	Garonne (karstic conduction)	0.340	0.248	0.156	0.064	0.276	81.2
G. de Salenques	Noguera-Ribagorzana	0.050	0.033	0.017	0.000	Vanished	100.0

781 *Area extrapolated from the 1984 and 2016 results, in order to provide an approximate decadal distribution of ice loss.

782

783 Table 2. Estimated annual volume loss of the remaining glaciers in the
784 Spanish Pyrenees. The abbreviation “G.” indicates “Glaciar”, the Spanish

785 word for “Glacier”.

Name	Watershed	V loss [m ³ yr ⁻¹]	V loss [m ³ s ⁻¹]	Source
G. del Infierno ^a	Gállego (Ebro)	156,396	0.00496	Marti et al. (2015)
G. de Monte Perdido ^b	Cinca (Ebro)	187,044	0.00593	López-Moreno et al. (2016)
G. de Llardana ^c	Cinca (Ebro)	53,824	0.00171	Julián and Chueca (2007)
G. de la Paul ^c	Esera (Ebro)	27,398	0.00087	Julián and Chueca (2007)
G. de la Maladeta	Esera (Ebro)	145,611	0.00462	Julián and Chueca (2007)
G. de Aneto	Esera (Ebro)	396,333	0.01257	Campos et al. (2020)

^a Data not available for this glacier. The data here provided was calculated using ice wastage data from a nearby (9 km) glacier (Ossue) with similar altitude and slope orientation.

^b Estimations from values of thickness loss.

^c Data not available for this glacier. The data here provided was calculated using ice wastage data from a nearby (16 km) glacier (Maladeta) with similar altitude and slope orientation.

786

787 Table 3. Flow volumes, glacier water contribution, and present and
788 predicted water demands in the Gallego, Cinca, and Noguera-Ribagorzana
789 Riber Watersheds (data sources: individual watershed reports from CHE,
790 2020; and authors' calculations).

Variables	Watershed		
	Gállego	Cinca (includes Esera River)	Noguera-Ribagorzana
Mean river flow [m^3s^{-1}]	12.50	80.87	17.90
Environmental flow [m^3s^{-1}]	3.44	4.61	2.00
Estimated glacier contribution [m^3s^{-1}] ^a	0.0050	0.0257	0.0000
Water necessary to satisfy household demand [m^3s^{-1}]	0.07	0.27 ^b	0.44
Water used for agriculture [m^3s^{-1}]	15.54	59.20	14.37
Water used for industry [m^3s^{-1}]	0.79	0.72	0.44
Basin area [km^2]	4020	6319	2061
Population served	35,000	105,533	142,072
River flow without glacier contribution [m^3s^{-1}]	12.50	80.84	17.90
Estimated conservative flow reduction due to climate change (12.5%) [m^3s^{-1}]	10.93	15.47	14.70
Remaining flow for household consumption [m^3s^{-1}]	-5.40	-44.45	-0.11

^a Based on annual melt.

^b There is no data on household requirements for this basin. Thus, the requirement here indicated is an estimation based on the data from the other two basins.

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